

Effect of Physical and Virtual Manipulatives on the Mathematical Achievement of Junior High School Students in the Topic of Transformation in Ghana

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Author's contribution

The sole author designed, analyzed and interpreted and prepared the manuscript.

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Abstract

There is a general perception that mathematics is difficult and many Junior High school students seem to struggle through mathematics lessons. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of physical (using mathematical set instruments) and virtual (using Geogebra software) manipulatives on the mathematical achievements of Junior High school students in the topic of Transformation (which is made up of rotation, reflection, enlargement/reduction by scale factor and translation). The topic was previously taught to the students by their teachers from their various schools. The researcher adopted a convenient sampling technique (with a sample size of 78 students) by making use of grade nine students (from 6 different Schools) who had enrolled in vacation classes at Ideal College of Ghana. Pretest-posttest control group experimental model, which is one of the quasi-experimental research designs, was used in the study. The students were randomly assigned to three different groups which consisted of two experimental groups and one control group. The pretest administered to all the groups showed that the mathematical achievements of the three groups were not significantly different. The data passed normality test and so ANOVA was applied in the analyses of pretest and posttest scores. One of the experimental groups was treated with physical manipulative and the other with a virtual manipulative. The control group was taught using the traditional method of teaching. One of the findings of the study showed that the use of manipulatives were significantly effective in increasing the achievement scores of the experimental groups. Another important finding showed that scores of low achievers were

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significantly improved when they were treated with manipulatives. Virtual manipulative proved to be more effective comparatively in increasing the achievements of grade nine students. It was recommended among many others that low achievers in mathematics should be given the opportunity to study with manipulatives.

Keywords: Geogebra; manipulative; junior high school; transformation.

1 Introduction

Dienes [1] proposed that learners' whose mathematical understandings were firmly grounded in manipulative experiences would be more likely to make connections between the world in which they live and the abstract world of mathematics. Effective teaching and learning of mathematics involves presenting the curriculum through multiple representations. Representations which can be used in mathematics education include physical (concrete), pictorial (static visual), and virtual (dynamic electronic) representations. In addition to the abstract (also referred to as symbolic) representations, math educators can use math manipulatives to model multiple representations of math concepts [2]. Many studies published between 1970 and 1990 supported the use of concrete math manipulatives. Researchers have found that students who used manipulatives during mathematical instruction typically outperformed the students who did not use the manipulatives [3]. These findings have been replicated in studies spanning across topics, grade levels, and ability levels). Several contemporary studies suggest that students with learning disabilities may benefit from using manipulatives more than main stream students do [4]. Regarding pictorial manipulatives, evidence suggests that they too are an important way for children to express their thinking as they develop an understanding of new math concepts [5]. According to Thompson & Thompson [6], teaching children how to utilize pictures to solve problems is a highly effective problem solving strategy. According to Moreno & Mayer [7], a distinguishing competency between high and low achieving math students is the ability to visualize math concepts. Moreover, Arcavi [8] reports that students who create, interpret, utilize, and reflect on pictorial representations may be able to link these representations to abstract concepts and subsequently develop a greater understanding to of the topics. Research on multiple intelligences and students' different learning styles supports the use of pictorial manipulatives [9]. With respect to virtual manipulatives, these tools have the potential to develop students' visualization skills by connecting words, pictures, and symbols simultaneously (Paivio [10]). According to Paivio [10], this coinciding presentation may help students develop a solid understanding of math concepts. According to a recent meta-analysis, using virtual manipulatives results in a moderate effect size of 0.44 compared to other instructional treatments [11].

Studies have shown that students using manipulatives in specific mathematical subjects are more expected to achieve success than students who don't have the chance to work with manipulatives. Mathematical concepts introduced with manipulatives enables students explore the concept using the manipulative in focused activity. As a matter of fact, for a long time, the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) has recommended the use of manipulatives in teaching mathematical concepts at all grade levels. The theory of experiential education spins around the idea that learning is enhanced when students acquire knowledge through active processes that engage them [12]. Manipulative can be key in providing effective, active, engaging lessons in the teaching of mathematics. Manipulative help students learn by allowing them to learn from concrete experiences to abstract reasoning [13]. Well-known math educator Marilyn Burns considers manipulatives essential for teaching math to students of all levels. She finds that manipulatives help make math concepts accessible to almost all learners, while at the same time offering sufficient opportunities to challenge students who catch on quickly to the concepts being taught. Research indicates that using manipulative is particularly beneficial for teaching low achievers, students with learning disabilities [14]. Research also indicates that using manipulatives helps improve the environment in math classrooms. When students work with manipulatives and then are given a chance to reflect on their experiences, not only is mathematical learning enhanced, math anxiety is greatly reduced [15]. Exploring manipulatives, especially self-directed exploration, provides an exciting classroom environment and promotes in students a positive attitude toward learning [16]. Among the benefits several researchers found

for using manipulatives was that they helped make learning fun [17]. Using manipulatives has been shown to help students reduce errors and increase their scores on tests that require them to solve problems [18]. The use of manipulatives helps students hone their mathematical thinking skills. According to Stein and Bovalino (2001), "Manipulatives can be important tools in helping students to think and reason in more meaningful ways. By giving students concrete ways to compare and operate on quantities, such manipulatives as pattern blocks, tiles, and cubes can contribute to the development of well-grounded, interconnected understandings of mathematical ideas." To gain a deep understanding of mathematical ideas, students need to be able to integrate and connect a variety of concepts in many different ways [19]. Clements (1999) calls this type of deep understanding "Integrated- Concrete" knowledge. The effective use of manipulatives can help students connect ideas and integrate their knowledge so that they gain a deep understanding of mathematical concepts. Though continuous use of manipulatives was emphasized by various researchers, teachers employ traditional methods in mathematics classes due to their biases regarding manipulatives including those prejudices such as that they do not know how to use the manipulatives, the manipulatives are not economical in terms of time and money, that the duration of the classes is inadequate, manipulatives cause some kind of cognitive confusion or they do not serve attainments of teaching. All of those prejudices of teachers about manipulatives lead to a decrease in the employment of manipulatives in the higher levels of education where the students have acquired abstract thinking skills, as opposed to the first years of education, when the manipulatives are used more often. It is the teachers' lack of information about how to use and manage the manipulatives that causes the decline in post-primary education. On the other hand, there are also some other researches putting forth that there is not a positive correlation between the manipulatives and mathematics achievement due to the prejudices of teachers against manipulatives and that manipulatives do not facilitate learning in mathematics instruction which have given way to studies that do not support the use of manipulatives in mathematics instruction. Thus, studies have emerged in literature, which drove inconsistent conclusions as to the effects of using manipulatives upon the achievement of students, especially with the students at higher levels of education, who have gained abstract thinking skills. This situation indicates to us that the effects of manipulatives on the achievement and attitude of students have yet not been explicitly clarified. Recently, there has been a promulgation of mathematics curricula that involve the use of manipulative materials, and many student-centered classrooms frequently employ the use of manipulatives during mathematics instruction. However, despite the wide availability of manipulatives and repeated calls for their use, some teachers continue to use more traditional approaches to mathematics instruction, citing cost, time constraints, and incongruence with skills measured on standardized assessments, and lack of training in how to teach using manipulatives. In addition, critics of the practical approach to mathematics have noted that the mere provision of manipulative materials is not likely to result in learning without specific instruction that supports students' model-based reasoning and conceptual understanding, which requires extensive teacher preparation and professional development in how children learn. In this regard, in order to inform the development of instructional materials and teacher training programs emphasizing manipulative use, it is important to establish an evidentiary basis for the use of manipulatives as an effective instructional practice in mathematics and to examine aspects of program implementation that may be associated with greater effectiveness [20]. To this end, the purpose of the present study is to summarize the existing evidence for manipulatives interventions and to investigate differential effects associated with participant, program, and study design characteristics [21].

1.1 Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of use of physical and virtual manipulatives on the mathematical achievement of JHS3 (grade 9) students in the topic of transformation. To this end, answers to following questions were sought:

1. Is there a significant difference between
 - a. Pretest scores of experimental and control groups?
 - b. Posttest scores of experimental and control groups?
 - c. Pretest-posttest scores of either group?

2. Is there a significant difference between
 - d. Boys who use manipulatives and boys who did not?
 - e. Girls who used manipulatives and girls who did not?
 - f. Boys and girls who used manipulatives?
 - g. Boys and girls who did not use manipulatives?
3. What is the impact of the use of manipulatives on low achievers in mathematics?
4. Which of the manipulatives (either physical or virtual) is best suited for the topic of Transformation?

2 Methods

The study sought to investigate the effect of physical and virtual manipulatives on academic achievement of JHS3 in the topic of Transformation in the JHS mathematics curriculum in Ghana. The researcher adopted a convenient sampling technique (with a sample size of 78 students) by making use of grade nine students (from 6 different Schools) who had enrolled in vacation classes at Ideal College of Ghana. Pre-test and post-test control group models (26 students in each group) which are one of the quasi-experimental designs, were used. Geogebra (virtual) mathematical software and Mathematical set intruments were used to teach Transformation to each experimental groups. The control group was taught using the traditional method of instruction without the use of a manipulative. A pretest was administered to each class at the beginning of the study and the results tested to ensure homogeneity of the groups. In order to reduce the effects of initial group differences on the results to be produced by the study, a pretest will serve as a covariate which will strengthen the experiment by removing an extraneous variable that could have a direct effect on the dependent variable (student achievement) [22]. A multiple choice test consisting of 20 items and oriented to “Transformation (rotation, reflection, translation and enlargement or reduction by scale factor)” topic in the learning domain of ninth grade mathematics lesson in junior secondary school was developed. KR-20 reliability coefficient of the achievement test was calculated as 0.82. This value demonstrates the reliability of the test as an assessment tool. In order to test whether the distribution of the scores obtained from the achievement of the student are normal, Shapiro-Wilk test is used if the sample size of the group is less than 50 and Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test is used if it is larger than 50 [23]. Shapiro- Wilk test was applied in this study, as the sample size was less than 50 and it was found that the observation values display normal distribution (Table 1). Since the distribution was normal, one way ANOVA was applied to the study. The research was carried out in three separate ninth-grade classes of ideal college school. Attention was paid that the classes would feature similar qualities in terms of their potentialities, during the selection of the classes. Designed teaching materials were tangible and allowed the students to practice and revise sufficiently.

2.1 Normal Q-Q plot

The output of the of a normal Q-Q plot can help determine normality graphically. If the data are normally distributed, the data points will be close to the diagonal line which is exactly the case in the Q-Q plots shown in Figs. 1 and 2. If the data points stray from the diagonal line would have meant the data are not normally distributed.

Table 1. Tests of normalityfor physical manipulatives group

Experimental 2	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^b			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Control	.298	4	.	.926	4	.572
	.237	5	.200*	.961	5	.814
	.197	11	.200*	.949	11	.634
	.260	4	.	.827	4	.161

Table 2. Tests of normality for virtual manipulative group

Experimental 1	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Control	.260	2	.	.920	8	.428
	.193	8	.200*	.874	7	.200
	.241	7	.200*	.822	6	.091
	.293	6	.117	.964	3	.637
	.253	3	.			

The table shows the results from two well-known tests of normality, namely the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test and the Shapiro-Wilk Test. The Shapiro-Wilk Test is more appropriate for small sample sizes (<50). For this reason we shall use the Shapiro-Wilk test as our numerical means of assessing normality. Shapiro-Wilk test is greater than 0.05, which implies the data is normal.

Fig. 1. Q-Q plot for experimental group 1

Fig. 2. Q-Q plot for experimental group 2

3 Results and Findings

Is there a significant difference between pretest scores of experimental and control groups before the application?

Table 3. Pre-test ANOVA of the different treatments

		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Experimental 1 (VM)	Between groups	10.367	6	1.728	1.389	.269
	Within groups	23.633	19	1.244		
	Total	34.000	25			
Experimental 2 (PM)	Between groups	8.854	6	1.476	1.108	.394
	Within groups	25.300	19	1.332		
	Total	34.154	25			

As shown in Table 3, there was no significant difference between the mathematics achievement mean scores of the experiment and control groups ($p > .05$). According to this finding, the mathematics achievement levels of the experiment and control groups before the application can be said to be equivalent.

Table 4. Pre-test descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	Std. deviation
Control	26	11.96	1.612
Experimental 1	26	12.00	1.166
Experimental 2	26	11.62	1.169
Valid N (listwise)	26		

Is there a significant difference between posttest scores of experiment and control groups after the application?

Table 4a. Post test ANOVA

		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Experimental 1 VM	Between groups	2.223	4	.556	2.970	.043
	Within groups	3.931	21	.187		
	Total	6.154	25			
Experimental 2 PM	Between groups	22.483	4	5.621	3.185	.034
	Within groups	37.056	21	1.765		
	Total	59.538	25			

According to the findings in Table 4, there was significant difference between the achievement posttest mean scores of experiment and control groups ($p < .05$). This finding indicates that manipulatives are effective in increasing the achievement scores of the experimental groups significantly.

Table 5. Post test descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	Std. deviation
Control post test	26	7.31	1.543
Experimental 1 (VM)	26	19.62	.496
Experimental 2 (PM)	26	12.81	1.021
Valid N (listwise)	26		

Is there a significant difference between the achievement pretest-posttest scores of the experiment and control groups?

Table 6. Pretest and Posttest ANOVA

		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
VMPr	Between groups	13.667	4	3.417	3.529	.024
	Within groups	20.333	21	.968		
	Total	34.000	25			
VMpo	Between groups	2.223	4	.556	2.970	.043
	Within groups	3.931	21	.187		
	Total	6.154	25			
PMPr	Between groups	5.406	4	1.351	3.134	.036
	Within groups	9.056	21	.431		
	Total	14.462	25			
PMpo	Between groups	22.483	4	5.621	3.185	.034
	Within groups	37.056	21	1.765		
	Total	59.538	25			

Table 6 shows a statistically significant difference in the achievement posttest scores of the experimental groups in comparison to their pretest scores.

- Is there a significant difference between boys who used manipulatives and boys who did not?
- Is there a significant difference between girls who used manipulatives and girls who did not?
- Is there a significant difference between boys and girls who used manipulatives?
- Is there a significant difference between boys and girls who did not use manipulatives?

Table 7. ANOVA table

			Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
MB * NMB	Between groups (Combined)		2.860	3	.953	2.035	.180
	Within groups		4.217	9	.469		
	Total		7.077	12			
MG * NMB	Between groups (Combined)		1.226	3	.409	.823	.513
	Within groups		4.467	9	.496		
	Total		5.692	12			

Table 8. ANOVA table

			Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
MB * NMG	Between groups (Combined)		3.160	3	1.053	2.421	.133
	Within groups		3.917	9	.435		
	Total		7.077	12			
MG * NMG	Between groups (Combined)		1.776	3	.592	1.360	.316
	Within groups		3.917	9	.435		
	Total		5.692	12			

*MB= Boys used manipulatives, NMB= Boys did not use manipulatives, MG= Girls used manipulatives
NMG= Girls did not use manipulatives*

It can be inferred from Tables 7 and 8 that:

- There is no significant difference between boys who used manipulatives and boys who did not ($p>0.05$).
- There is no significant difference between girls who used manipulatives and girls who did not ($p>0.05$).
- There is no significant difference between boys and girls who used manipulatives ($p>0.05$). There is no significant difference between boys and girls who did not use manipulatives ($p>0.05$).

Table 9. Manipulative use and gender 1 descriptive statistics

	Mean	Std. deviation
MB	13.38	.768
MG	14.15	.689
NMB	13.00	1.000
NMG	12.62	1.044
Valid N (listwise)		

What is the impact of the use of manipulatives on low achievers in mathematics?

Table 9a. Low achievers ANOVA

		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Experimental VM	Between groups	16.056	1	16.056	6.677	.036
	Within groups	16.833	7	2.405		
	Total	32.889	8			
Experimental PM	Between groups	18.000	1	18.000	6.300	.040
	Within groups	20.000	7	2.857		
	Total	38.000	8			

It can be deduced from Table 9 that there is a significant difference between the scores of students when the traditional method of teaching was used (control) against when physical and virtual manipulatives were introduced to them. By extension, students who performed below average were found to have their achievements (scores) significantly improved when they were introduced to the treatments (physical and virtual manipulatives).

Table 10. Low achievers descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	Std. deviation
control	9	7.33	2.179
Experimental PM	9	11.67	.500
Experimental VM	9	17.11	2.028
Valid N (listwise)	9		

Which of the manipulatives (either physical or virtual) is best suited for the topic of Transformation?

With reference to Tables 5 and 10, virtual manipulatives proved to be more effective in increasing the achievements of grade nine learners in the topic of transformation. This conclusion can be realized by comparing the average scores of students when physical and virtual manipulatives were utilized.

4 Conclusion

Findings of this study show that prepared teaching materials increase the mathematics achievement of the students, which can be explained by the treatment of manipulatives as a connection concretizing abstract mathematical concepts. In reference to the comparison of achievement posttest scores of the experiment and control groups, the high scores in the posttest of the experimental groups indicates that the manipulatives prepared for the "Transformation" and topic contributed extensively to effective learning. In summary the findings of the study are as follows:

- There was no significant difference between pretest mean scores of experimental and control groups ($p > .05$).
- There was significant difference between the achievement posttest mean scores of experiment and control groups ($p < .05$).

- Manipulatives were found to have effectively enhanced the achievement scores of the experimental groups significantly.
- There was no significant difference between boys who used manipulatives and boys who did not ($p>0.05$). There was no significant difference between girls who used manipulatives and girls who did not ($p>0.05$). There was no significant difference between boys and girls who used manipulatives ($p>0.05$). There was no significant difference between boys and girls who did not use manipulatives ($p>0.05$).
- Students who performed below average were found to have their achievements (scores) significantly improved when they were introduced to the treatments (physical and virtual manipulatives).
- Virtual manipulative proved to be more effective in increasing the achievements of grade nine learners in the topic of transformation than the physical manipulative.

5 Recommendations

In the view of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are crucial to the effective teaching and learning of mathematics in the Junior High School.

1. Workshops for mathematics teachers need to be sanctioned by the various stakeholders of education in Ghana on the need to adopt the use of manipulatives in teaching.
2. Low achievers in mathematics should be given the opportunity to study with manipulatives.
3. The mathematics curriculum should be restructured to encourage the use of manipulatives in teaching and learning.

Competing Interests

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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Appendix

Pre test

Subject: Mathematics _____

Name of Student: _____

Circle: The Correct Answer_ Duration: 1 ½ Hours_ Topic: Transformation

Level: Grade Nine

- Find the image of the point $(-2, 4)$ when it is reflected on the x-axis.
A. $(-2, -4)$ B. $(2, -4)$ C. $(2, 4)$ D. $(4, -2)$
- Find the image of the point $(5, -1)$ when it is rotated 90° anticlockwise about the origin.
A. $(-1, 5)$ B. $(-1, -5)$ C. $(1, -5)$ D. $(1, 5)$
- Find the image of the point $(3, 7)$ when it is rotated 90° clockwise about the origin.
A. $(7, 3)$ B. $(7, -3)$ C. $(-7, -3)$ D. $(-7, 3)$
- Find the image of the point $(-2, -10)$ when it is rotated 180° clockwise about the origin.
A. $(-10, -2)$ B. $(-2, -10)$ C. $(10, 2)$ D. $(2, 10)$
- Find the image of the point $(5, 0)$ when it is rotated 270° clockwise about the origin.
A. $(0, 5)$ B. $(0, -5)$ C. $(5, 0)$ D. $(-5, 0)$
- Find the image of the point $(8, -9)$ when it is reflected on the line $x = 0$.
A. $(-8, 9)$ B. $(-8, -9)$ C. $(8, 9)$ D. $(-9, -8)$
- Find the image of the point $(-1, 4)$ when it is reflected on the mirror line $y = x$.
A. $(-1, -4)$ B. $(4, -1)$ C. $(-4, -1)$ D. $(1, -4)$
- Find the image of the point $(-6, 3)$ when it is reflected on the mirror line $y = -x$.
A. $(6, -3)$ B. $(-6, -3)$ C. $(6, 3)$ D. $(-6, 3)$
- Find the image of the point $(5, -5)$ when it is rotated 270° anticlockwise about the origin.
A. $(-5, -5)$ B. $(-5, 5)$ C. $(5, 5)$ D. $(5, -5)$
- What image will be produced if the point $(-7, 12)$ is translated by the vector $\begin{pmatrix} 3 \\ -4 \end{pmatrix}$?
A. $\begin{pmatrix} -4 \\ 8 \end{pmatrix}$ B. $\begin{pmatrix} 8 \\ -4 \end{pmatrix}$ C. $\begin{pmatrix} 15 \\ -13 \end{pmatrix}$ D. $\begin{pmatrix} -13 \\ 15 \end{pmatrix}$

11. What translation vector was used to transform the point (4, 2) to produce the image (-5, 7)?
- A. $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -9 \end{pmatrix}$ B. $\begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 9 \end{pmatrix}$ C. $\begin{pmatrix} 9 \\ 5 \end{pmatrix}$ D. $\begin{pmatrix} -9 \\ 5 \end{pmatrix}$
12. If the translation vector $\begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 9 \end{pmatrix}$ transforms a point to produce the image of (2, 3), find the point.
- A. (3, -6) B. (-3, 6) C. (6, -3) D. (-6, 3)
13. If the image of the point P(3, -4) is P¹(-3, 4) then the transformation applied is
- A. Reflection with x -axis a mirror line
 B. Rotation of 90° about the origin
 C. Translation by vector $\begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$
 D. Use of scale factor -1 about the origin
14. Which of the following is property or are properties of enlargement?
- I. If the scale factor (k) is larger than 1 or smaller than -1 , then the enlargement is a magnification
 II. If the scale factor (k) is between 1 and -1 , then the enlargement is a reduction
 III. If the scale factor (k) is negative, the object and the image are on opposite sides of the centre of the enlargement.
- A. I only B. II only C. I and II only D. I , II, and III
15. Find the image of the point (10,4) when a scale factor of -1/2 about the origin is applied
- A. (5, 2) B. (-5, -2) C. (-5,4) D. (5,-4)
16. One side of the image of a triangle is 2 and the corresponding side of the object is 6. Find the scale factor.
- A. 12 B. 1/3 C. 3 D. 1/12
17. Which is/are true?
- I. A shape has Rotational Symmetry when it still looks the same after a rotation (around a central point).
 II. The number of times a shape matches when we go once around after one full rotation is called the Order.
 III. Translation is a slide, reflection is a flip and rotation is a turn of an object.
- A. I only B. I and III only C. I and II only D. I, II and III
18. Which is/are true?
- I. After transformations such as turn, flip or slide the shape still has the same size, area, angles and line lengths.
 II. rectangles, squares, circles, and all regular polygons have rotational symmetry
 III. If you turn an object through 180 degrees around its center and at any point the object appears exactly like it did before the rotation, then the object has rotational symmetry.
- A. I only B. I and III only C. I and II only D. I, II and III

19. Which is/are true?

- I. The letter Z has rotational symmetry but no line symmetry
- II. Letter O has both line symmetry and rotational symmetry
- III. Letter A has line symmetry but no rotational symmetry

A. I only B. I and III only C. I and II only D. I, II and III

20. Which is/are true?

- I. In a complete turn of 360° , the number of times an object looks exactly the same as it is given is called the order of rotational symmetry
- II. Line symmetry occurs when a shape or image is reflected across a line.
- III. The three basic kinds of 2-dimensional symmetry are reflection, rotation, and translation

A. I only B. I and III only C. I and II only D. I, II and III

Post test

Subject: Mathematics _____

Name of Student: _____

Answer any two questions_ Duration: 1 hour_ Topic: Transformation

Level: Grade Nine

1. a. Using a scale of 2 cm to 2 units on both axes, draw on a graph sheet of paper two perpendicular axes, Ox and Oy for the interval $-10 \leq x \leq 10$ and $-10 \leq y \leq 10$.

b. Draw on the same graph sheet

I. $\triangle ABC$ with A (2, 2), B (4, 6) and C (6, 2).

II. The image $\triangle A'B'C'$ of $\triangle ABC$ under reflection with the y-axis as a mirror line where

$$A \rightarrow A', B \rightarrow B', C \rightarrow C'.$$

III. The image $\triangle A''B''C''$ of $\triangle ABC$ under anticlockwise rotation through 90° about the origin where $A \rightarrow A'', B \rightarrow B'', C \rightarrow C''$.

IV. The image $\triangle A'''B'''C'''$ of $\triangle ABC$ under enlargement by scale factor -1 about the origin where

$$A \rightarrow A''', B \rightarrow B''', C \rightarrow C'''.$$

2. a. Using a scale of 2 cm to 2 units on both axes, draw on a graph sheet of paper two perpendicular axes, Ox and Oy for the interval $-10 \leq x \leq 10$ and $-10 \leq y \leq 10$.

b. Draw on the same graph sheet

I. The quadrilateral $ABCD$ with A (2, 2), B (6, 2), C (8, 8) and D (4, 8)

II. The image quadrilateral $A_1B_1C_1D_1$ of quadrilateral $ABCD$ under anticlockwise rotation through 180° about the origin where $A \rightarrow A_1, B \rightarrow B_1, C \rightarrow C_1, D \rightarrow D_1$.

- III. The image quadrilateral $A_2B_2C_2D_2$ of $A_1B_1C_1D_1$ under reflection on the x-axis where $A_1 \rightarrow A_2, B_1 \rightarrow B_2, C_1 \rightarrow C_2, D_1 \rightarrow D_2$.
- IV. The image quadrilateral $A_1B_1C_1D_1$ of quadrilateral $ABCD$ under enlargement by scale factor -1 about the origin where $A \rightarrow A_3, B \rightarrow B_3, C \rightarrow C_3, D \rightarrow D_3$.
3. a. Using a scale of 2cm to 2 units on both axes, draw on a graph sheet of paper two perpendicular axes, Ox and Oy for the interval $-10 \leq x \leq 10$ and $-10 \leq y \leq 10$.
- b. Draw on the same graph sheet
- I. $\triangle ABC$ with A (1, 1), B (5, 1) and C (4, 5).
- II. The image $\triangle A'B'C'$ of $\triangle ABC$ under translation by the vector $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$ where $A \rightarrow A', B \rightarrow B', C \rightarrow C'$.
- III. The image $\triangle A''B''C''$ of $\triangle A'B'C'$ under clockwise rotation through 90° about the origin where $A' \rightarrow A'', B' \rightarrow B'', C' \rightarrow C''$.
- IV. The image $\triangle A'''B'''C'''$ of $\triangle A''B''C''$ under enlargement by scale factor -1 about the origin where $A \rightarrow A''', B \rightarrow B''', C \rightarrow C'''$.

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